

The Influence of Physical Self-Concept and Mental Toughness on Sports Performance of Student-Athletes

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Abstract. Poor sports performance among school athletes is a global concern. This study explores the physical self-concept, mental toughness, and sports performance among a quota sample of 150 student-athletes. Results indicate that student-athlete respondents sometimes manifested self-concept in all four dimensions: sports competence, physical conditions, and body attractiveness. On one hand, they reported high levels of rebound ability, ability to handle pressure, concentration ability, and confidence, all considered dimensions of mental toughness in this study. Similarly, they perceived strong sports performance across all five dimensions: athlete development, mastery and development, strategy and preparedness, recovery and injury prevention, and psychological skills. Furthermore, multiple linear regression analysis highlights mental toughness as a significant influence on sports performance, emphasizing its critical role in fostering athletic success among student-athletes. Recommendations are discussed.

KEY WORDS

1. Physical Education, 2. student-athletes 3. physical self-concept
4. mental toughness 5. sports performance

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1. Introduction

The declining sports performance of student-athletes is a significant issue impacting educational institutions worldwide (Yukhymenko-Lescroart, 2021). A troubling trend is that student-athletes need to meet expected performance benchmarks, leading to concerns about the effectiveness of current training and support systems (Bates et al. (2024). Empirical data supports this concern, revealing a widespread problem of student-athletes failing to meet athletic performance standards (Lopes Dos Santos et al., 2020). About 50% of student-athletes indicate that their sports performance is declining in the US (Johnson, 2022). Also, around 35% of student-athletes in Indonesia need help

to meet performance standards in their sports disciplines. This decline is evident in their reduced competitiveness and achievement levels in national and regional competitions (Anindya et al., 2022). Moreover, approximately 45% of student-athletes in Bangladesh report declining sports performance. This problem affects both individual and team sports, as many athletes do not meet the expected performance standards set by their institutions (Salcinovic et al., 2022). The situation in the Philippines is equally worrying. A recent study by Capio et al. (2023) found that 45% of student-athletes reported a significant decline in their athletic performance in the past year. Billonid et al. (2020), a larger

systemic issue is reflected in the fact that within the last five years, one-fifth of student-athletes competing in national competitions have fallen behind. Deterioration in student athletic performance has significant implications for their future career paths and academic standing, such as diminished chances of earning scholarships and boosted prestige in college (Karimi, 2021; Roscigno, 2023). Also, the devaluation of athletic performance sabotages the overall development of student-athletes, leading to negative

effects on their well-being and potential for success in later sports (Till et al., 2022). Urgent action is needed to address this problem, as continued declines can have long-term negative effects on the health, well-being, and professional opportunities of student-athletes. The aim of this study is to explore physical self-concept, mental toughness, and sports performance among student-athletes, providing a basis for potential interventions.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design—This non-experimental quantitative study had a two-fold purpose: To describe the physical self-concept, mental toughness, and sports performance among student-athletes, and then examine how the first two variables influenced the latter. More specifically, this study aimed to address the following four research objectives:

- (1) To describe the level of physical self-concept of student-athletes in terms of sports competence, physical conditions, body attractiveness, and physical strength;
- (2) To describe the level of mental toughness of student-athletes in terms of rebound ability, ability to handle pressure, concentration ability, and confidence;
- (3) To describe the level of sports performance of student-athletes in terms of athlete development, mastery and development, strategy and preparedness, recovery and injury prevention, and psychological skills;
- (4) To examine the extent to which physical self-concept and mental toughness would influence the sports performance of student-athletes.

2.2. Research Locale—The respondents were from a prominent educational institution

located in the Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte, Philippines. With a student population of more than 4,000, it was recognized as one of the best schools in the area for providing excellent education. By choosing student-athletes from this institution, the research gained a new perspective because it tackled an area of education that had not been extensively studied before. This was particularly noteworthy. That school's attention contributed to raising athletic performance levels and highlighting its increasing role as a source of quality education on the island.

2.3. Theoretical Framework—Self-efficacy theory, developed by psychologist Albert Bandura in 1977, centers on individuals' beliefs in their capacity to accomplish tasks or achieve goals, influencing cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects of functioning. In this study, physical self-concept is an independent variable and comprises four aspects; namely, sports competence, physical conditions, body attractiveness, and physical strength (Shannon, 2011). As another independent variable, mental toughness, also means believing in personal mental capacity, is composed of the various aspects, as follows: rebound ability, ability to handle pressure, concentration ability, and confidence (Anselmo Go, 2021). Sports

performance is the dependent variable, which comprises the following five aspects: athlete development, mastery and development, strategy and preparedness, recovery and injury prevention, and psychological skills. The hypothesized relationship is illustrated in a conceptual framework shown below.

2.4. Research Respondents—A quota sample of 150 college student-athletes were the respondents of the study. They were enrolled in SY 2023-2024 at a local community college, with a student population of around 4,000, located in the Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte, Philippines. According to Simkus (2023), quota sampling involves selecting participants based on specific characteristics, which ensures that the selected individuals accurately represent certain attributes relative to their prevalence in the population.

2.5. Research Instrument—The researcher used the book *Examining the Influence on Self* by Shannon (2011) to adapt and modify the physical self-concept and athletic identity of former college athletes to obtain data on the independent variable of physical consistency. The questionnaire was initially modified and restructured to incorporate the diverse tools employed. Specifically, the Physical Self-Perception Profile (PSPP), the Athlete Identity Measurement Scale (AIMS), the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSE), and the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ). In this study, the level of physical self-concept of the student-athletes is evaluated using the following Likert rating scale: 5 as strongly agree, 4 as agree, 3 as neutral, 2 as disagree, and 1 as strongly disagree. The table that follows describes the description and interpretation according to the range of means.

Ranges of Means Description Interpretation

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20—5.00	Very High	This means that the physical self-concepts of student-athletes are always manifested.
3.40—4.19	High	This means that the physical self-concepts of student-athletes are often manifested.
2.60—3.39	Moderate	This means that the physical self-concepts of student-athletes are sometimes manifested.
1.80—2.59	Low	This means that the physical self-concepts of student-athletes are seldom manifested.
1.00—1.79	Very Low	This means that the physical self-concepts of student-athletes are never manifested.

The instrument underwent a reliability test, and the statistical output for the Physical Self Concept scale indicates a high level of internal consistency with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.957, suggesting that the scale is a reliable tool for measuring how individuals perceive their physical selves. The data set, with all 30

valid cases and no exclusions, ensures a complete assessment across the sample. The mean score of 75.1333 with a standard deviation of 17.51400 across 24 items indicates that while there is an average level of physical self-concept among the participants, there is also a moderate range of variability in individual scores, reflect-

ing diversity in physical self-perception within the group. To gather data for the independent variable, which was mental toughness, the researcher adapted and modified the questionnaire used in "Mindfulness, Mental Toughness, and Motivation as Correlates of College Students' Sports Involvement: Basis for a Proposed Guide for School Administrators" by Anselmo and Go (2021). The questionnaire had a 5-point rating scale for the construct of mindfulness during sports activities, mental toughness during sports activities, motivation to get involved in sports, and sports involvement. Moreover, this questionnaire was originally from the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) by Brown and Ryan (2003), the Mental Toughness Inventory (MTI) by Middleton et al. (2011), and the Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS) of Deci (1985) and Ryan et al. (1991). In evaluating the level of mental toughness of the student-athlete, the respondents used the following in rating the

questionnaire: 5 as strongly agree, 4 as agree, 3 as neutral, 2 as disagree, and 1 as strongly disagree. The Likert scale below was used to analyze the result: The reliability testing exhibits internal solid consistency with a Cronbach's Alpha of .935, indicating that the items on the scale are well-correlated and likely measure the same underlying construct effectively. With 30 valid cases and no exclusions, the comprehensive dataset suggests a representative measure of the sample's mental toughness. The mean score is relatively high at 85.3667, with a standard deviation of 14.76829, indicating a moderate spread around the mean, though the participants tend to rate themselves as mentally challenging. This spread of scores reflects some variability in mental toughness among participants, while the consistency of the scale suggests it could be reliably used in further research or practical applications.

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To gather data for the dependent variable, which was sports performance, the researcher adapted "The Sports Performance Perceptions Scale (SPPS) Manual" by Adam et al. (2023). The SPPS was a multidimensional self-report measure of perceived athletic performance that required minimal time to administer, minimal

administrator training, and low to no financial resources. It could be used by athletes participating in any sport. All items were answered using a 5-point Likert scale. In evaluating the level of sports performance of the student-athlete, the respondents used the following in the questionnaire: 5 as strongly agree, 4 as agree, 3 as neu-

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1.00—1.79	Very Low	This means that the sports performance of student-athletes is never manifested.

With reliability test results, the statistical summary for the Sports Performance scale suggests a very high level, with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.962, indicating that the scale’s 30 items consistently measure the intended construct of sports performance. The data set, with all 30 valid cases and no exclusions, ensures a complete assessment across the sample. The mean score is quite high at 110.5000, paired with a standard deviation of 20.54725, which points to a relatively wide spread of scores. This means that while the average sports performance score

is above the scale’s midpoint, individual scores vary significantly, with some participants likely performing much higher or lower than the mean. The large number of items on the scale could contribute to capturing a broad range of aspects of sports performance. Furthermore, the instrument underwent validation testing, achieving an impressive average score of 4.55. This validation indicates that the tool utilized was deemed valid, thus affirming its suitability for use in the study’s execution.

2.6. Data Gathering Procedure—Pre-Data Gathering. The researcher sought clearance and a certificate from the Research Ethics Committee (REC). For the research to yield benefits and minimize the risk of harm, it had to be conducted ethically. The researcher requested clearance from the research ethics committee to ensure that the research was conducted to protect the respondents’ dignity, rights, and safety and that the research design was ethically sound and likely to produce the expected

results. Additionally, ethical approval for a research project enhances the legitimacy of research findings, which is crucial for making decisions based on the research results. Following the clearance from REC, the researcher sought an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of Holy Cross of Davao, with the consent of the thesis adviser, to conduct a study with the title, student-athletes Sports Performance: Exploring the interplay of physical self-concept and mental toughness. With

the endorsement letter, the researcher submitted a request letter to the President of the Samal Island City College to conduct the study. After receiving the approval letter from the President of the Samal Island City College, the researcher forwarded a letter to the College Deans under Study. The data-gathering procedures for the study involved several processes, all of which were executed ethically. Administration and Retrieval of Informed Consent. Before administering the questionnaire, the researcher ensured the informed consent of all respondents. The researcher diligently briefed students on completing the provided consent forms, with the College President and Dean's explicit endorsement and unwavering support. Each item within the consent forms was translated into the local dialect during the survey to guarantee respondent comprehension and accurate responses. Subsequently, student-athletes at the institution engaged with the consent process. Upon completion, the researcher promptly retrieved all consent forms via email, ensuring respondents had conscientiously and comprehensively provided all necessary information. Administration and Retrieval of Questionnaires. The researcher adequately explained to the students and their

teachers how to respond to the provided questionnaires with the approval and full support of the College President and Dean. The researcher translated each question from the indicators into their dialect during the survey administration to ensure the respondents understood each question and provided accurate replies. Student-athletes at the school answered the instrument. The researcher retrieved all the completed questionnaires by submitting the survey through email address after the respondents had honestly and thoroughly filled out the questionnaire and provided all the essential data. Tabulation and Organization of Data. The administration and retrieval of the questionnaires occurred, and the survey questionnaires were effectively administered and received. Following this, the researcher ensured that all gathered data was meticulously stored and explicitly committed to not utilizing it for any other study. Using appropriate statistical equipment, the researcher obtained data for interpretation and further analysis. The researcher's dedication to preserving the confidentiality and integrity of the data was demonstrated by the careful handling of its management, which reinforces the importance of ethical research practices.

2.7. *Data Analysis—Mean.* According to Kaliyadan (2019), Using a representative value in the analysis of variance, the average level of each variable can be determined and thus support the inference of the main characteristics of the respondents. To gain insight into typical or average experiences, this study used an analysis of mean statistics to analyze important variables such as physical self-esteem and mental toughness. Several sports were represented by athletes in the sample. Respondent statistical methods were employed to evaluate these variables. Pearson-r. Pearson-r is a tool that measures the size and direction of correlations between different variables (Stewart, 2024). This

study analyzed the Pearson-R used to determine the relationships between athletes' physical self-concept, mental toughness, and athletic performance. This helped the researcher understand the relationship between psychological factors and athletic performance by explaining the nuanced interaction of these characteristics in a specific population of student-athletes. Multiple Regression Analysis. The study conducted by Micoogullari (2017) highlights the importance of multiple regression in revealing how student athletes' levels of physical self-esteem and mental toughness affect their athletic performance. In this study, the researcher used multiple regression analysis to build a regression model

that identified the specific influence and relative importance of these psychological factors on sports performance and discovered whether they work independently or interactively in shaping sports performance.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Level of Physical Self-Concept of Student-Athletes*—The level of physical self-concept of student-athletes in terms of sports competence, physical conditions, body attractiveness, and physical strength. Provided in Table 1 is the answer to this objective.

Table 1. Level of Physical Self-Concept of Student-Athletes

Physical Self-Concept	Mean	Descriptive Level
Sports Competence	3.13	Moderate
Physical Conditions	3.31	Moderate
Body Attractiveness	3.14	Moderate
Physical Strength	3.05	Moderate
Overall	3.16	Moderate

Table 1 describes the level of physical self-concept of student-athletes in terms of sports competence, physical conditions, body attractiveness, and physical strength. The results indicate that student-athletes have a moderate level of physical self-concept across various dimensions. The levels of sports competence (M = 3.13), physical conditions (M = 3.31), body attractiveness (M = 3.14), and physical strength (M = 3.05) all fall within the moderate range, leading to an overall moderate physical self-concept score of 3.16. This suggests that, on average, student-athletes perceive their physical abilities and attributes at a moderate level, indicating a balanced but not highly confident or exceptionally low self-view in these areas.

Student-athletes must possess a reasonable level of physical confidence in all aspects. Stults-Kolehmais and Sinha (2019) revealed that adult athletes' exercise behavior and mental well-being are influenced by their physical self-concept, with those having moderate levels of self-esteem more likely to exercise reg-

ularly and report higher subjective well-being compared to those with excessively high or low self-esteem. This highlights the importance of a balanced self-concept in promoting physical activity and mental well-being. Similarly, Kim and Ahn (2021) demonstrated that athletes require an ideal physical self-concept to remain motivated and maintain a healthy psychological state, a conclusion also supported by Liu et al. (2023). Liu et al. surveyed 300 college students to assess their physical self-image and exercise behavior, finding that students who perceived themselves in better physical shape were more likely to exercise regularly, although adherence varied. Duarte-Clímets et al. (2020) further emphasized that exercise intentions and behavior are heavily influenced by physical self-concept, highlighting the importance of maintaining regular exercise through positive self-perception.

Johnson et al. (2017) investigated body image perceptions and social comparison tendencies among 200 student-athletes, finding

that they frequently feel good when comparing their bodies to peers, despite inconsistent beliefs about their body shape. This indicates that student-athletes engage in socially comparable body image processes, believing they can maintain a desired body. The highest physical self-concept score (M = 3.14) was in body attractiveness, indicating moderate confidence among student-athletes in their appearance and competence in various sports. Krauss and Orth (2022) explored self-concept's impact on talent growth in youth sports, finding that competence influences motivation, skill development, and performance, thereby enhancing self-esteem and athletic growth. Rodrigues et al. (2024) fur-

ther found that positive self-images are linked to higher motivation and better performance in youth sports, emphasizing the importance of a balanced self-image.

The lowest indicator of physical self-concept was physical strength (M = 3.05), indicating varied perceptions among student-athletes. Terry et al. (2022) found that perceptions of physical strength fluctuate over time, influenced by factors such as performance history, injuries, and training experiences (Rice et al., 2016). These findings underscore the importance of a balanced and positive self-concept in athletic performance and development.

Table 2. Level of Mental Toughness of Student-Athletes

Mental Toughness	Mean	Descriptive Level
Rebound Ability	3.56	High
Ability to Handle Pressure	3.69	High
Concentration Ability	3.72	High
Confidence	3.58	High
Overall	3.64	High

Shown in Table 2 are the levels of rebound ability, ability to handle pressure, concentration ability, and confidence under the main construct “mental toughness” of student-athletes. The results indicate that student-athletes have a high level of mental toughness across various dimensions. The mean scores for rebound ability (3.56), ability to handle pressure (3.69), concentration ability (3.72), and confidence (3.58) all fall within the high range, leading to an overall high mental toughness score of 3.64. This suggests that, on average, student-athletes are adept at recovering from setbacks, managing stress, maintaining focus, and possessing confidence, which are essential traits for athletic performance and success.

The overall high level of mental toughness suggests that athletes are resilient, determined,

and able to maintain focus and perform well under pressure. It allows them to overcome challenges, bounce back from setbacks, and perform at their best, even in difficult circumstances. This also agrees with Mladenovic and Trunic (2019), who state that the best participants in sports can rebound from the defeat and adversity they face before and during participation. More specifically, a high level of concentration ability indicates that student-athletes often demonstrate strong concentration abilities. Moreover, it implies that they often prioritize performing at their best in every game and derive satisfaction from knowing they've given their all. This result supports the descriptive and experimental evidence from Moran (2017) and Jones et al. (2019), who found that student-athletes with superior concentration skills re-

ported higher levels of overall mental toughness. The ability to handle pressure is a highly rated indicator of mental resilience among students, with a mean of 3.69 described as high. This suggests that respondents emphasize giving their best performance in every game and are satisfied knowing that they have worked hard even under pressure. This supports Poulus et al. (2020), who found that student-athletes who use appropriate coping strategies are mentally tougher. These athletes can handle setbacks and failures more effectively, which improves their mental strength. Effective load management is crucial in competitive sports, as athletes often face intense situations where they must perform at their peak despite external stressors.

Confidence received the third-highest average score of 3.58, which is described as high. Regardless, the mental toughness of student-athletes often comes from self-confidence. Student-athletes often find themselves at the center of an anchor's strength during the most challenging moments of the game, which is when their self-confidence shines. They can be confident in their abilities and overcome challenges by having a self-belief, regardless of the circumstances. It's important to have con-

fidence in yourself. This supports research on students with high self esteem who tend to be more motivated, resilient, and persistent (Chiou et al., 2020). Confidence is essential for athletes who prioritize both academic and athletic endeavors. Self-confidence and mental toughness are frequently cited as the hallmark traits of student-athletes. Finally, a high-level rebound ability (or to recover) indicates that student-athletes frequently exhibit resilience and determination when they overcome setbacks or encounter obstacles, using these experiences as catalysts for improvement. This resonates with the findings of Connaughton et al. (2018), who conducted a longitudinal study and found that athletes who improved their endurance over time also improved their mental toughness. This demonstrates the potential for resilience to be enhanced through practice and experience. A study conducted by Galli and Vealey (2016) aimed to determine the psychological resilience of individuals recovering from sports injuries. Collegiate athletes possess the ability to overcome obstacles, learn from mistakes, and maintain a resilient mindset. This is particularly true in higher education settings.

Table 3. Level of Sports Performance of Student-Athletes

Sports Performance	Mean	Descriptive Level
Athlete Development	3.42	High
Mastery and Development	3.68	High
Strategy and Preparedness	3.61	High
Recovery and Injury Prevention	3.70	High
Psychological Skills	3.68	High
Overall	3.62	High

The sports performance levels of student-athletes in athlete development, mastery and development, strategy and preparedness, recovery and injury prevention, and psychological skills are shown in Table 3. The results indi-

cate that student-athletes exhibit a high level of sports performance across various aspects. The mean scores for athlete development (3.42), mastery and development (3.68), strategy and preparedness (3.61), recovery and injury pre-

vention (3.70), and psychological skills (3.68) all fall within the high range, leading to an overall high-level sports performance score of 3.62. This suggests that student-athletes are highly proficient in their development, skill mastery, strategic planning, recovery practices, and psychological skills, which are crucial for achieving and sustaining high performance in sports.

The overall high level indicates that student-athletes perform efficiently in their sports, reflecting their dedication, skill, and enthusiasm (Gould et al., 2017). These findings align with Gould et al. (2017), who highlighted the importance of physical and mental preparation, skills such as goal-setting, imagery, and self-talk, as well as efficient coaching and support systems. Lin et al. (2017) also emphasized mental toughness, resilience, and stress management for high athletic performance. Among the five indicators, recovery and injury prevention received the highest average score, showing that student-athletes recognize the significance of rest and injury rehabilitation for their overall performance and long-term success (Jayanthi et al., 2020; Aldanyow AlOrain, 2024). This indicates a proactive approach to managing performance through injury prevention and management.

Mastery and development, and psychological skills were the second highest indicators, demonstrating student-athletes' commitment to training and competition, essential for skill development and peak performance (Dweck, 2016; Pohl Nelson, 2020). These findings suggest that student-athletes develop substantial mental capabilities, enhancing their sports achievements. "Strategy and preparedness" is another key factor, indicating student-athletes' willingness to follow coaching strategies and take breaks during training to maximize potential (Williams Hodges, 2017; Williams Jones, 2020). This proactive approach to strategic planning and preparation shows their dedication to maximizing athletic performance. Finally, athlete development, though the lowest among the indicators, still reflects a high level of development. This indicates that student-athletes prioritize their growth, support teammates, and recognize the significance of their primary sport in fostering teamwork and leadership (Anderson Pierce, 2009). These findings suggest that student-athletes not only focus on their own development but also support peers in achieving shared success.

Table 4. Significance of the Relationship Between the Physical Self-Concept and Mental Toughness to Sports Performance of Student-Athletes

Sport Performance	Self-concept	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Interpretation				
Physical Self-concept Significant		.583	.000	Reject
Mental Toughness Significant		.817	.000	Reject

This finding echoes the study by Shuai et al. (2023), who found that higher physical self-esteem in athletes is moderately related to improved athletic performance because it increases motivation and self-confidence. Simi-

larly, Lohbeck et al. (2021) showed that physical self-concept links physical aspiration and self-esteem, which improves overall athletic performance. These studies, when taken together, highlight the significance of elevating student

athletes' body image to enhance their performance. The statistics demonstrate a clear correlation between mental toughness and athletic performance in student-athletes, with a p-value (.000) indicating strong statistical significance. This means that greater mental toughness is associated with better athletic performance. A correlation coefficient of 0.817 supports this, indicating a strong positive relationship. These outcomes demonstrate the significance of cultivating student mental resilience for enhanced performance. These findings echo the study of Wu et al. (2021), which emphasizes the strong relationship between mental toughness and sports performance, showing that higher levels of mental toughness led to better performance outcomes. Similarly, Park and Jeon (2023) found a positive correlation between mental toughness and physical endurance in male rowers, further highlighting that increasing mental toughness

can improve athletes' performance. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Physical Self-Concept and Mental Toughness on the Sports Performance of Student-Athletes Table 5 presents the outcomes of hypothesis testing regarding the influence of mental toughness and physical self-concept on sports performance among student-athletes. The overall analysis indicates a significant relationship between the predictor variables and sports performance, with an F-value of 152.163 and a p-value of 0.000, surpassing the conventional significance level of 0.05. Specifically, Ho2, which hypothesized a positive relationship between mental toughness and sports performance, is positively rejected. This rejection is supported by a notably low p-value of 0.000 and a robust beta coefficient of 0.802. Each unit increase in mental toughness corresponds to a significant improvement of 0.802 in sports performance.

Table 5. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Physical Self-Concept and Mental Toughness on the Sports Performance of Student-Athletes

Sports Performance	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	B	Std. Error	Beta	T
Constant			0.361	0.192		1.875
Mental Toughness			0.802	0.065	0.751	12.285
Physical Self-Concept			0.107	0.064	0.103	1.686

$R = .821$; $R^2 = .674$; F-value = 152.163; p-value = .000

Conversely, Ho3, which posited a significant influence of physical self-concept on sports performance, is not rejected. A p-value greater than 0.05 is associated with the physical self-concept; athletic performance is not significantly influenced by physical self-concept. The significant R-squared value of 67.4% of focus points to the importance of mental strength and physical self-esteem in sports performance—the crucial psychological factor affecting an athlete's success is their mental ability to perform. These results show that interventions and training programs designed to build mental resilience can help athletes perform better at sports. This is consis-

tent with the study by Stomamani et al.(2020), which revealed that mental toughness was a significant factor in athletic performance across different sports, including individual and team. Based on regression analysis, their study suggests that athletes' mental resilience is a crucial factor in driving them to perform at the highest level possible in competitive sports. Furthermore, Simonsmeier and Buecker (2017) have identified mental toughness as one of the key attributes for an athlete's success, which includes self-assurance, focus, and determination. Mental toughness plays a vital role in the success of athletes.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The findings of the study suggest an advantage in integrating a psychological skills training program for student-athletes, which includes enhancing rebound ability, stress management, concentration, and confidence. By systematically developing these mental toughness skills, schools can help athletes better handle competitive pressures and enhance their overall sports performance. Moreover, the present study did not consider cultural factors that could moderate or mediate the relationships between or among physical self-concept, mental toughness, and sports performance. Comparative studies across different cultural contexts can also offer valuable insights into the universality versus specificity of these psychological constructs in athletic settings.

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